

Digital Teacher Supervision in Yemen

Reflections on a pilot implementation

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Abbreviations and acronyms

FCDO	UK Foreign, Commonwealth & Development Office
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICO	Information Commissioner's Office (UK Government)
KII	Key Informant Interview
REAL	Restoring Education and Learning

1. Introduction

This report presents findings from a rapid study that captures the experiences and perceptions of supervisors and teachers regarding the use of digitally enabled teacher supervision in Yemen. The study was commissioned by the World Bank and funded by the United Kingdom's Foreign Commonwealth and Development Office (FCDO). The study aimed to help the World Bank and its partners strengthen future digital supervision in Yemen by capturing good practice examples and lessons from a recent pilot implementation.

This section includes details of the study background, scope and research questions. [Section 2](#) presents an overview of the study methodology, including the chosen approaches to data collection, sampling, and analysis, as well as ethical considerations and limitations. The findings and discussion are presented in [Section 3](#), followed by a conclusion in [Section 4](#) and recommendations in [Section 5](#).

1.1. Study background

Yemen continues to face severe humanitarian pressures. Recent reporting estimates that around 18.2 million people—almost half of the population—are in need of humanitarian aid, including 17.6 million people with severe needs, reflecting the wider pressures of conflict, economic crisis, disrupted public services, and climate-related shocks ([↑UK Home Office, 2025](#)).

These wider pressures have also had serious implications for education. Recent reporting notes that 3.7 million children aged 5 to 17 are out of school, while many of those still attending face overcrowded classrooms, damaged or under-resourced learning environments, and teachers who are overworked, unsupported, or unpaid in some areas ([↑UNICEF, 2025](#); [↑UNICEF, 2026a](#)). The education crisis is also reflected in very weak learning outcomes. UNICEF reports that 94.7% of 10-year-olds in Yemen are unable to read and understand a simple text ([↑UNICEF, 2025](#)).

The Restoring Education and Learning (REAL) project is funded by the World Bank and delivered by Save the Children, the World Food Programme, and UNICEF in Yemen ([↑World Bank, 2020](#)). It aims to improve access to basic education through a focus on improving learning conditions, providing alternative education pathways, and enhancing teacher capacity. This involves supporting school functioning and learning

recovery by working directly with schools, teachers, and local education structures ([UNICEF, 2026b](#)).

Between January and June 2025, the project piloted digital data collection tools in Yemen to monitor reading programmes, teacher and principal training, remedial learning, and learning assessments. Digital forms replicated Ministry of Education supervision tools and were distributed via secure links using tablets. Nearly 4,000 submissions were collected, providing progress data at the start and end of the reading programme.

Within the Yemen REAL project, digital supervision was introduced to strengthen and standardise the monitoring of classroom practice, teacher performance, and broader school-level conditions. Based on information shared by a World Bank consultant involved in the work, digital classroom supervision was intended to enable supervisors to collect data during school visits, document observations, verify visits through Kobo geo-coordinates, and generate information for review and follow-up at district and central levels. The shift from paper-based to digital reporting was also intended to improve the timeliness and accessibility of supervision data for the Ministry of Education, implementing partners, and the World Bank.

1.2. Study scope

Following the pilot, the World Bank sought EdTech Hub's support to document and refine good practices in tool development, training content, and deployment, and to generate practical advice for near-term implementation. This included examining supervisors' and teachers' experiences of observing and being observed using digital supervision tools, and exploring how this supervision approach can be refined to strengthen teachers' technical practice while accounting for existing system constraints.

To this end, this study was designed to generate timely and practical insights into the implementation of digital classroom supervision in Yemen. The purpose was not to evaluate the programme, but rather to understand how digital supervision has been experienced, what conditions support or hinder its use, and what is needed to strengthen implementation and inform future scale-up. The study focused on four broad areas:

1. Current supervision practices;
2. Supervisors' experience of using digital supervision tools;
3. Implementation barriers and enabling conditions;
4. Data protection and safeguarding considerations.

It is important to note that this study is one of a three-part response to the World Bank's request for support. It should therefore be read in conjunction with an EdTech Hub report on early learner classroom observation and teacher performance tools ([Mufti et al., 2026](#)), as well as the AI Observatory's landscape analysis exploring how AI can be used to support assessment activities ([Jetten et al., 2026](#)).

1.3. Research questions

The study aims to respond to the following questions:

1. How was digital supervision used to observe, record, and support early-grade instructional practices?
2. How were supervision activities perceived by supervisors and teachers?
3. What individual, organisational, institutional, and contextual challenges and enabling factors affected the implementation of digital supervision, or could impact future implementation and scale-up?
4. Given these factors, how could digital tools be used to strengthen teacher supervision practices in Yemen in future?
5. How do participants in the supervision understand and experience digital security and safeguarding?
6. How can stakeholders ensure that digital supervision is conducted without compromising participants' safety, dignity, or integrity?

2. Methodology

The study combined a small number of qualitative methods to capture different relevant perspectives while working within a tight timeframe. It is important to note that these methods were not intended to generate statistically generalisable findings; rather, the aim was to capture a useful spread of perspectives across relevant participant types and implementation contexts to inform future programme iterations. Details of the methods chosen, the research team's approach to sampling, data collection and analysis, and the limitations encountered are presented in this section.

2.1. Data collection methods

Data collection followed an adaptive approach. While the original design included consultations with a broader range of stakeholders, including staff from Save the Children and the Yemeni Ministry of Education, the scope had to be adjusted in response to access constraints, stakeholder availability, and the short study timeline. As a result, data was generated through interviews with supervisors and teachers and a questionnaire completed by expert informants, and supplemented by discussions and written responses from the World Bank. These methods were also used alongside the desk review data generated by EdTech Hub for a report on classroom observation and teacher performance tools ([↑Mufti et al., 2026](#)).

2.1.1. Key informant interviews

Key informant interviews (KIIs) were conducted with supervisors and teachers, some of whom had experience with digital supervision and others who did not. Two flexible interview protocols were developed (one for supervisors, one for teachers). The supervisor protocol focused on supervision practices, prior use of digital tools (where applicable), operational barriers, support needs, and suggestions for improvement. The teacher protocol focused on experiences of being observed, perceptions of digital supervision, feedback processes, and implementation challenges. In cases where teachers had not yet experienced digital supervision, these questions were reframed as hypothetical to gauge teachers' readiness and appetite for digital supervision, as well as their broader experiences with it.

Interviews were conducted in Arabic via Google Meet, averaging 45 minutes. With participants' consent, discussions were audio recorded. Tactiq (an AI notetaker) was used to generate Arabic transcripts, alongside

structured notes; these were then quality assured and translated into English in preparation for systematic analysis.

2.1.2. Written responses from experts

In addition to the KIIs, the research team developed a set of questions for expert informants to respond to in writing. This was intended to capture more specialised reflections on programme feasibility, implementation realities, and data governance issues from stakeholders who could not easily be reached through live interviews.

The questionnaire and accompanying consent form were sent to two expert informants identified through the research team's professional networks. Both had relevant experience in low-resource and crisis-affected contexts, including work related to implementation, education in emergencies, and digital risk. Written responses were returned by both experts and used to complement the KIIs, particularly regarding data protection, privacy, security, and safeguarding considerations.

2.2. Sampling and recruitment

Sampling for the KIIs followed a purposive approach. The aim was to select a small but information-rich sample that reflected some diversity in gender, location, supervision experience, and prior exposure to the earlier REAL programme.

2.2.1. Sampling criteria

The minimum target was three teachers and three supervisors, with attention to gender balance and location. The broader intention was to include participants with differing levels of prior exposure to supervision activities and, where possible, varying prior experience with the REAL programme. Meanwhile, expert informants were selected based on their knowledge of data protection and security concerns in contexts comparable to Yemen in terms of stability and resource availability. In applying these criteria, the final selection also considered practical factors such as accessibility and the availability of participants within the study timeline.

2.2.2. Recruitment process

For the KIIs, the World Bank provided the research team with a list of 14 potential supervisors and teachers, which had in turn been provided by the

Ministry of Education. From this list, a final sample of six interviewees was selected: three teachers and three supervisors. These individuals were selected to achieve a balanced sample across gender, experience, and location. A breakdown of the final KII sample is provided in [Table 1](#) below.

Table 1. KII and expert informant sample

Participant code	Gender	Location	Experience of digital supervision?
Teacher 1	Female	Abyan	No
Teacher 2	Male	Hadramout	Yes
Teacher 3	Female	Abyan	No
Supervisor 1	Male	Hadramout	No
Supervisor 2	Male	Aden	Yes
Supervisor 3	Male	Abyan	Yes
Expert 1	Female	N/A	N/A
Expert 2	Male	N/A	N/A

In parallel, two expert interviewees were identified through the research team’s professional networks to provide additional insight into data protection, privacy, security, and safeguarding in unstable and low-resource settings. Expert 1, Nothando Mtungwa, is a Research Analyst with Open Development & Education and EdTech Hub. Her work focuses on special educational needs and disabilities, interventions, and implementation research across Malawi, Kenya, Rwanda, Ghana, and Eswatini. Particularly relevant to the Yemen context, she has also conducted research on education in emergencies, bringing expertise in how educational programmes operate under conditions of fragility, disruption, and heightened safeguarding risk. Expert 2 was Dr Calvin Zakaria Swai of the University of Dodoma, Tanzania, whose experience in educational technology and technology-supported teacher professional development provided an additional perspective on digital implementation in resource-constrained settings. These expert interviews were not intended to be nationally representative; rather, they were included to strengthen the analysis of practical risks, safeguards, and contextual considerations relevant to the Yemen study.

All participants were contacted directly via WhatsApp to introduce the study, confirm willingness to participate, and schedule the interview at a mutually convenient time.

2.3. Data analysis

Data was analysed in Google Sheets using an analytical framework based on the research questions. The analysis was both deductive and inductive; while findings were grouped into predetermined analytical categories, codes were generated inductively within these. The framework was also kept flexible to allow for the addition of new themes that had not been anticipated but would nevertheless add value to the study findings.

AI-assisted tools were used selectively to support aspects of drafting and language refinement during write-up. Their use was limited to improving clarity of presentation and did not replace researcher-led coding, interpretation, or analysis.

2.4. Ethical considerations

This study involved a small number of qualitative interviews with teachers, supervisors, and expert informants and therefore required clear procedures to protect participants' privacy, support informed participation, and minimise risks associated with handling personal and institutional data. Given the sensitivity of the Yemen context, particular attention was paid to confidentiality, secure data handling, and the separation of identifiable information used for research operations from the anonymised material used for analysis and reporting.

All participants were provided with information about the study before the interview. The consent process explained the purpose of the research, what participation would involve, the voluntary nature of participation, and participants' right to decline to answer individual questions or to stop the interview at any point. It also clarified how interview data would be used, how confidentiality would be protected, and who would have access to the data. Where interviews were audio recorded, participants were informed of this in advance, and recording proceeded only after consent was obtained. Contact details and other identifying information collected for scheduling and consent administration were used only for research operations and were not included in analysis outputs.

To protect anonymity, names were replaced with participant codes at the point of transcription and analysis, and identifying details were removed from research materials used for reporting. In practice, this meant that

respondents were referred to only by role-based participant codes, such as Teacher 1 or Supervisor 2, rather than by name. School names, contact details, and any location information that could reasonably contribute to identifying an individual were excluded from quoted material and analytic outputs. Given the small sample size and the conflict-affected setting, anonymisation was approached conservatively, with care taken to avoid combinations of details that could make participants identifiable even where direct names had been removed.

Data-handling procedures were governed by a formal data-sharing agreement between EdTech Hub and the World Bank. This agreement distinguishes between identifiable data required for research operations and anonymised primary data shared for learning and decision-making purposes. Identifiable personal data, such as names and contact details used for scheduling and consent administration, were stored securely on the EdTech Hub Drive and accessed only by the relevant research team members. Access was controlled through internal policies, including restricted permissions and two-factor authentication, and work devices used for data collection were password protected. The agreement also specified that downloading or printing personal data would be minimised, and that any hard copies would be destroyed on completion of data collection.

Audio recordings, transcripts, and other primary materials were handled in line with a data minimisation approach. Un-anonymised materials were retained only for as long as necessary for transcription, cleaning, and analysis. Audio recordings and anonymised transcripts were scheduled for destruction on completion of the study period in March 2026. Before any primary data was shared with the World Bank, materials were cleaned and anonymised by removing direct and indirect identifiers. Anonymised data was not to be shared with third parties without the World Bank's explicit agreement.

These measures were important not only for compliance with the study's data management procedures but also because the risks associated with disclosure in this context could be significant. The study, therefore, sought to ensure that participants could contribute views on teacher supervision and digital tools without unnecessary exposure of their identities, schools, or local contexts.

2.5. Limitations

The research team encountered the following limitations over the course of this study.

Sample size. The study relied on a small purposive sample of six interview participants. While this enabled in-depth exploration of user experiences and implementation realities, the findings cannot be considered representative of all teachers and supervisors involved in digital supervision in Yemen. The sampling strategy prioritised variation and information-rich perspectives rather than broad coverage.

Reliance on self-reporting. The study findings are largely drawn from participants' own accounts of their practices and perceptions. As with most qualitative studies of this kind, responses may be influenced by recall bias, interpretation of events, or a tendency to frame experiences in particular ways. The analysis sought to mitigate this by comparing perspectives across participant groups and triangulating with available programme documentation and stakeholder inputs.

Stakeholder availability. The study also faced practical constraints in stakeholder engagement. For example, direct input from Save the Children could not be secured during the study period because the relevant team for the new programme had not yet been established.

Compressed timeline. The research was conducted within a short timeframe (approximately six weeks). This required data collection and analysis to proceed in parallel, limiting opportunities for iterative refinement of research tools, follow-up interviews, or extended validation processes. As a result, the study prioritised generating timely and practical insights rather than undertaking a more extensive system-level assessment.

Sampling constraints. The study relied on key informant details being provided by the Ministry of Education, and it is unclear on what basis the suggested participant list was created. This may have led to the participant sample containing an uneven spread of views. In addition, there was a notable gender imbalance within the list, with no female supervisor details provided. Time constraints prevented the research team from requesting additional contacts to balance the sample, though effort was made to do so as far as possible by ensuring that two of the three teachers were female.

Potential lack of participant candour. It is possible that participants felt indirect pressure to provide 'appropriate' or positive responses regarding their supervision experiences, out of fear of negative consequences if they were critical. This possibility was minimised by reassuring participants that all responses would be anonymised in reporting.

Connectivity and access constraints. Contextual constraints required interviews to be conducted remotely via Google Meet. Weak connectivity in participants' locations disrupted some interviews, and audio quality was poor at times. Connectivity conditions further limited which participants and regions could be reached in practice, potentially underrepresenting experiences from less accessible areas, where implementation realities may differ.

3. Findings and discussion

Findings from the supervisor and teacher KIIs, as well as the responses from expert informants, are presented in this section. These are organised broadly in line with the research questions.

Please note that participants are referred to throughout using an assigned participant code (T1 = Teacher 1; S2 = Supervisor 2, and so on). It may also be helpful to bear in mind that participants responded in line with the extent of their experience with digital supervision; in some cases, they refer to supervision activities in general, as they have not specifically experienced digital supervision. Effort has been made to distinguish between the two as far as possible.

It is also important to bear in mind that these findings reflect the experiences of an early-stage pilot, which is typically used to identify issues and develop solutions prior to scaling. The findings are therefore not intended to be evaluative but rather to support future programme iterations.

3.1. How was digital supervision used to observe, record, and support early-grade instructional practices?

3.1.1. Supervision was often framed as supportive, but not always experienced that way

Both teachers and supervisors described supervision as intended to provide pedagogical guidance and identify areas for professional improvement. Teachers commonly referred to receiving verbal feedback and practical recommendations following classroom observations. As one teacher noted, “The supervisor gives us feedback after the lesson, and this helps us improve in the next class” (T3). Supervisors similarly described school visits as developmental in purpose. One supervisor explained that visits were intended not “to monitor, inspect, or hunt for mistakes, but to assist in the implementation of the lesson or the achievement of the programme” (S2). This approach is reflected in the fact that supervision visits were reportedly always announced in advance, indicating an intention to provide structured support for teachers rather than ‘catch them out’.

At the same time, this supportive framing did not fully remove anxiety or evaluative pressure from the experience of being observed. Interviewees

indicated that teachers could still feel nervous during visits and, in some cases, adjust their behaviour in response to being observed. One teacher, for example, suggested that unannounced visits might sometimes give a more accurate picture of classroom practice, explaining: “Sometimes teachers decided to be absent once they know that the supervisor will visit” (T3). This suggests that, even where supervision was presented as developmental, it could still be experienced in ways that encouraged performative behaviour or avoidance. This indicates that significant effort must be put into gaining teachers’ trust over time and helping them feel at ease with supervision processes to ensure that observations generate genuinely reliable and helpful data.

3.1.2. The extent of digital tool usage within supervision activities during the pilot was limited in practice

Participants’ receptiveness to digital supervision did not translate into consistent routine use. In practice, the adoption of digital tools depended on whether tablets had been distributed, how reliable connectivity was during school visits, and whether administrative requirements or financial reimbursement processes continued to prioritise paper records. Two supervisors in different locations (S2, S3) described maintaining hybrid documentation processes, using both paper and digital tools during the same visit. Another supervisor, who had not participated in the pilot, felt he would need to retain paper documentation as a safeguard against technical failure and as a reference for future evaluations (S1) if switching to digital supervision. These accounts suggest a level of caution towards the full adoption of digital tools, and also that digital supervision was introduced alongside existing manual reporting systems rather than replacing them, limiting the anticipated gains in efficiency during the pilot phase. Some possible reasons for this dual approach will be discussed in [Section 3.5](#).

In contrast, one supervisor described using his phone to photograph and make video recordings of classroom activities and teacher–student interactions to support peer learning among teachers (S1). Visual materials were also sometimes shared through informal communication channels, such as WhatsApp groups, allowing teachers to observe classroom practices and exchange practical teaching approaches. The fact that this practice was reported by a supervisor who had no experience of the pilot (which involved the use of observation forms completed on a tablet) suggests that the use of visual documentation for professional learning was not exclusively linked to the introduction of digital supervision tools.

3.1.3. Whether paper-based or digital, it is unclear what happens to supervision data once submitted

Supervisors reported that completed supervision tools, regardless of format, were ultimately transmitted to central Ministry of Education structures, but they had limited visibility into how this data was subsequently used. Paper-based reporting was described as involving multiple administrative steps, including retaining copies at the school level, submitting originals to directorates, and later transferring information into Excel files before central submission. One supervisor highlighted the lack of feedback following this process; as they explained, “After that, this Excel file is sent to the centre and remains there. Unfortunately, there is no feedback on this.” (S1). Another supervisor similarly noted, “We knew only about submitting reports to the global partnership programme” (S2). These accounts suggest that governance arrangements were not always visible or well understood. This limited feedback loop suggests that supervision data was perceived primarily as compliance outputs rather than as inputs into instructional improvement or system learning.

3.2. What benefits of digital supervision did participants experience?

3.2.1. Digital supervision improved the speed of reporting

Participants with experience of tablet-based supervision most consistently emphasised the speed with which reports could be completed and transmitted. Compared with paper-based processes, which could require several days for write-up, compilation, and onward submission, digital tools were described as enabling much more immediate reporting. One supervisor explained that paper-based reports previously took up to three days to prepare, whereas tablet-based reporting allowed information to be delivered “at the same moment” (S2). Another similarly noted that digital tools made it possible for the report to be ready by the end of the day of the school visit (S1).

Furthermore, some respondents reported that digital supervision facilitated greater transparency around supervisory activities. As one supervisor explained,

“[W]ith the tablet, they receive the report at the same moment, so they know the supervisor was in that directorate on that day and whether the report was positive or highlighted some concerns.” (S2)

These perceived efficiencies are especially important given the context of heavy supervisor caseloads and pressurised schedules. Supervisors described working under substantial time pressure, which affected the number of teachers who could be observed, the depth of engagement during each visit, and the ability to sustain meaningful follow-up. As one respondent noted, “According to the Ministry laws, the supervisor should have 50 teachers. Now I have 100, even above 100” (S1). Others similarly described the challenge of visiting multiple teachers within a single school visit, which reduced the time available for observation, documentation, and feedback (S3).

3.2.2. Digital supervision supported standardisation and completeness

Digital supervision was described as supporting more standardised and complete reporting. This point emerged mainly from the accounts of supervisors with prior direct experience of tablet-based supervision, while teachers were less able to comment on these practical benefits because they were being observed rather than completing the tools themselves. Supervisors contrasted tablet-based systems with paper-based processes, which could be affected by missing fields, calculation errors, or inconsistencies in completion. As one supervisor explained,

“[S]ometimes we forget to document some numbers, or we forget to add the numbers, but if we have a digital programme, then it will directly notify us that there is something missing in the tool or a mistake.” (S2)

Another supervisor similarly noted that the tablet made it easier to complete evaluation scores and follow the reporting structure. Although based on a limited number of respondents, these accounts suggest that digital supervision may improve reporting quality not simply by digitising existing processes, but by embedding prompts and checks that support more consistent completion and reduce avoidable errors.

3.2.3. Digital supervision simplified data entry, management, and retrieval

Digital supervision is also associated with greater ease of use in completing, handling, and retaining supervision records. Supervisors described tablet-based tools as more convenient than paper-based systems, particularly when observations had to be recorded, scored, analysed, and submitted within a short period. One supervisor stated

plainly that “the tablet is easier”, explaining that paper records were retained mainly as supporting evidence rather than because they were more practical to use (S3). Another (S2) noted that the tablet made it easier to manage evaluation scores, complete the report more efficiently, and store information for later reference.

These accounts suggest that the perceived value of digital supervision extended beyond faster reporting alone. It also lies in simplifying the practical work of documentation and creating stronger possibilities for storing and retrieving records over time. For supervision systems, this is important because easier handling and retention of records may support more cumulative use of supervision data, including follow-up across visits and reference to earlier observations where functionality allows.

3.3. What benefits of future digital supervision do participants anticipate?

3.3.1. Participants associate digital supervision with modernisation and professionalisation

Participants without direct experience of tablet-based supervision often viewed it positively and saw it as a means of supporting wider educational development and improvement. In these accounts, digital supervision was not only associated with possible practical benefits, but also with a broader aspiration towards progress, modernisation, and greater alignment with more advanced ways of working. One teacher described the idea positively, calling it “a new programme to develop education in our country” (T1).

This sense of aspiration was also reflected in how some participants spoke about moving beyond older paper-based approaches and, at times, drew comparisons with practices in other countries. As one supervisor explained, “I don’t want to carry a pen and paper or a notebook. I wish I had a computer or a tablet with me, and that has actually been achieved as part of our ambitions” (S2). In this sense, digital supervision appeared to carry both symbolic value and practical appeal. It was not seen simply as a new administrative tool, but as a visible step towards a more modern, outward-looking education system.

3.3.2. Digital supervision could support continuity, effective monitoring, and information retention

For participants both with and without direct experience, the perceived value of digital tools extended beyond the immediate act of recording

observations and was linked to the possibility of more consistent monitoring over time. One respondent, for example, emphasised the importance of “continuity and permanence of work, not just a temporary phase that ends” (S3), while another simply noted that “with tablets, there would be more continuity” (T1). These accounts suggest that anticipated benefits were closely tied to a desire for supervision systems that feel more stable and capable of supporting ongoing engagement rather than one-off visits.

Participants also linked this continuity to being able to retain information more systematically over time. One teacher suggested that digital supervision would be “more supportive” because “the supervisor will store my information” (T3). Here, the perceived benefit was not only that records could be captured digitally, but that they might remain available for later reference and follow-up. This points to an expectation that digital tools could help make supervision more cumulative, with stored information potentially supporting stronger monitoring and more sustained support across visits.

3.3.3. Digital supervision could reduce teacher anxiety

Evidence of the Hawthorne Effect—the psychological phenomenon that occurs when people behave differently if they know that they are being observed (↑[Spencer & Mahtani, 2017](#))—is clearly present in participants’ supervision accounts. As noted in [Section 3.1](#), teachers reported modifying their behaviour during observed lessons, with one explaining,

“Definitely, I will be more effective when the supervisor visits me. I interact more when I teach the lesson. That way, he gets a good impression of me.” (T3)

In parallel, one supervisor flagged that this was an issue that could be at least partially addressed by the introduction of digital supervision, reflecting that visible note-taking during observations could increase teacher anxiety, but tablet-based data entry might reduce this anxiety to some extent:

“I’m evaluating the teachers during class. I feel when I write about them, and if I write a lot, they get confused and worried. So I had to take a small note paper and write down the most important things. But maybe when we have the tablet, we will just click one time or twice, so we don’t confuse the teacher.” (S1)

3.4. What participant-level factors influenced the implementation of digital supervision, or could impact future implementation?

3.4.1. Participant support for technology use is an important prerequisite for effective digital supervision

Openness and enthusiasm for digital supervision provided a favourable foundation for implementation. Across interviews, both teachers and supervisors often expressed positive views about the use of tablets in supervision, with little evidence of outright opposition to the idea itself. Two teachers made broadly positive statements about technology in the classroom in general (“We like to have it”—T2). Supervisors were similarly receptive, with one noting that “all supervisors welcomed the tablet idea” (S3), while another described digital supervision as having “a lot of great value” (S1). While this openness did not, by itself, resolve the practical and institutional barriers affecting implementation, it meant that digital supervision was being introduced into a context where the tool itself was broadly acceptable to those expected to use or receive it.

Conversely, the supervisor who noted the “great value” of digital supervision also expressed doubt about whether electronic records could be securely preserved over time, reinforcing his preference to retain paper documentation. He questioned the capacity of digital systems to support the long-term storage and retrieval of supervision records needed for future performance monitoring and administrative accountability:

“It can be dangerous in terms of the device breaking down or something like this. So it’s necessary to have something on paper. It should be in the files for the future. For example, I want to evaluate a teacher in five or ten years. If, for example, the device breaks down or something like that, and I don’t have anything on paper, there will be a problem.” (S1)

This is important because effective uptake depends not only on positive attitudes towards technology, but also on confidence in how digital systems work in practice (↑[Tauson & Stannard, 2018](#)). In contexts where digital awareness remains uneven, participants may welcome digital supervision while still feeling uncertain about data preservation, system reliability, and the shift away from paper-based records, suggesting that future uptake during continuation or scale-up of the pilot is likely to require clear explanations and practical reassurance to build confidence in the digital system.

3.4.2. Prior exposure and general digital readiness may have a meaningful impact on digital supervision effectiveness

Interview accounts indicated that familiarity with tablet-based supervision varied considerably across participants and settings. While some, particularly those involved in earlier pilots, could describe digital supervision in concrete terms, others had had little or no exposure to it. Several teachers and supervisors reported that they had not participated in, or even heard of, the use of digital tools for supervision. As one supervisor explained, “I did not participate. A group of directors participated in a programme [...] tablets were distributed, but for supervision it wasn’t used” (S1). Similarly, one teacher stated simply, “I didn’t hear about it” (T1).

In some cases, this limited exposure appeared to reflect a broader lack of familiarity with digital approaches in education. As one teacher observed, “people don’t know what the digital programme is, and people don’t know what e-learning is” (T3). This suggests that digital supervision may be introduced into settings where broader digital awareness and preparedness remain limited. It also points to an important distinction in how different actors encountered the process. Supervisors described the direct use of tablets for observations and reporting. In contrast, teachers’ awareness was typically indirect, reflecting their role as the subjects of supervision rather than the users of the tool itself. While this difference is consistent with programme design, it reinforces the risk that teachers may be expected to participate in digitally supported supervision without a clear understanding of how it operates.

3.4.3. Transparency around the supervision process supported successful implementation

Digital supervision processes seem to have been facilitated by transparency regarding the purpose and content of the digital tools. One supervisor described giving teachers the device they were using “to see its items and told them to take a photo so they could use it for next visits” (S2). As a result, the same supervisor noted that “All the teachers that I visited felt it was very normal. No one asked about the tablet.” In a similar vein, another supervisor explained that,

“From a human relations perspective, we made them feel that this digital performance was only for development and improvement, not for monitoring or, for example, sending it to other places or authorities. The teacher was very responsive to us in this regard.” (S3)

Teachers similarly emphasised the importance of transparency in conducting observations. As one teacher explained, “The teacher must know exactly which tool the supervisor is using during their class, and how the supervisor is evaluating me.” (T1). Another highlighted expectations for clearer developmental feedback, stating,

“I would like the supervisor to train me on the tool itself. Like one time when the supervisor visited me and used the laptop during the lesson, he didn’t say anything [...] he just kept silent.” (T3)

These accounts suggest that the organisation and framing of supervision visits were closely linked to broader perceptions of trust and professional support. In contexts where supervision was clearly communicated as developmental, participants appeared more receptive to both supervisory processes and the introduction of digital tools.

3.5. What organisational and institutional factors influenced the implementation of digital supervision, or could impact future implementation?

3.5.1 Delayed device availability and administrative requirements during the pilot negatively impacted the integration of digital tools into supervision routines

As noted in [Section 3.1](#), supervision reporting remained largely hybrid throughout the pilot. Supervisors described recording observations either directly on tablets or first on paper, then transferring the information into digital systems. This pattern was shaped both by delays in tablet distribution and by administrative requirements that continued to prioritise manual documentation, particularly for financial verification. In relation to the former, late device provision meant that digital tools were used only during a limited number of visits, reducing their practical value within the pilot programme cycle (S3). At the same time, dual documentation was sometimes required for financial verification processes. As one supervisor noted,

“The World Bank has branches in the provinces. Sometimes they didn’t receive the reports, so the financial director asked for paper records so he could give us the money.” (S2)

Despite these procedural requirements, the same supervisor expressed a favourable view of digital supervision, noting that the use of tablets increased efficiency and reduced reporting time. These accounts indicate that, despite positive attitudes towards digital supervision in principle,

procurement delays and institutional reporting expectations combined to hamper the integration of digital tools into established supervision routines during the pilot.

3.5.2 Device- and platform-related issues limited successful implementation

Tool-related constraints appear to have limited how smoothly digital supervision could be implemented in practice. Participants with prior experience of digital supervision (S2, S3) described several design and usability issues affecting the digital observation forms they were expected to complete via their tablet, including:

- Inability to edit mistakes once information has been entered
- Mismatched school codes within the system
- Interface limitations that make information difficult to view
- System slowness
- Overly long tools that are difficult to navigate during visits

These technical problems indicate issues at the design level, and highlight an important learning for future implementation and scale-up. Care should be taken to create observation tools that are compatible with the devices used, accurately display the relevant school data, and align with the practical demands of supervision visits, including connectivity levels.

3.5.3. Digital supervision was hampered by limited local troubleshooting capacity

Interview findings suggest that supervisors had limited access to structured technical support while conducting school visits, particularly when using digital supervision tools in remote or low-connectivity areas. When technical challenges arose, such as device malfunctions, software errors, or difficulties synchronising data, supervisors often relied on informal peer assistance rather than formal support mechanisms. As one supervisor described,

“For example, I was in Hadramaut implementing the programme on my first visit. Then I encountered a problem before I started the visit, and I asked a colleague who has skills, and he helped me. I invited him to the hotel where I was staying, and he gave us better ideas.” (S2)

Participants further indicated that technical support functions were largely centralised at the Ministry level, with no dedicated support structures

available at the governorate level. This was perceived as limiting the timeliness and effectiveness of assistance during field implementation and contributing to uncertainty regarding clear escalation pathways for technical issues. One supervisor emphasised the need for more localised support arrangements, stating,

“We also faced difficulties in terms of getting help from the support team. I should have a support team in the governorate, a technical support team that can solve the problem directly. This would facilitate the work, but there are also difficulties in this regard.” (S3)

This centralisation of support meant that supervisors often had to manage technical disruptions independently during visits, which could affect the continuity and reliability of digital supervision activities. In practice, the absence of local troubleshooting mechanisms may slow response times, increase reliance on informal solutions, and reduce confidence in the system’s responsiveness during implementation.

3.5.4. Uneven and insufficient training provision may have led to inconsistent digital supervision implementation

Interview accounts suggested that digital supervision was not introduced within a uniformly supported or consistently organised system. In some cases, participants described patchy implementation across locations, including training opportunities. One supervisor noted that training activities had taken place only in selected areas:

“We held these training sessions in Maarab and in some directorates, not in all governorates. For example, in Hadramaut, only in Mukalla, in one directorate, and in Maarab, in one directorate, and in Taiz, in only two directorates”. (S2)

During training, supervisors noted that sessions were too brief to adequately prepare them for digital supervision activities. One reported that the training workshop he attended lasted only three days, “two days of which were spent updating the devices” and only “one day for how to use it” (S3). Another similarly recalled that training on the device and Kobo system lasted only “an hour or an hour and a half” (S2). Beyond training on the tablet itself, one supervisor also indicated that deeper digital skills training was also required, which would not have been possible in the limited training he was offered: “I need to be trained on digital skills, not only to train me on how to use [the] tablet and press on this button and that button” (S3).

Uneven training provision and programme awareness may therefore be at least partially responsible for the varied digital supervision approaches and experiences cited in [Section 3.1](#), suggesting that it will be important in further implementation and scale-up to ensure that all supervisors and teachers can equally enjoy the potential benefits of digital supervision.

3.6. What contextual factors influenced the implementation of digital supervision or could impact future implementation?

3.6.1. National economic issues negatively influence all supervision activities, including digital supervision

Financial, salary, and transport constraints emerged as a significant operational concern in participants' accounts. Interviewees described digital supervision as introduced in a context of wider economic strain, where low salaries, limited compensation, and the practical costs of travel affected what teachers and supervisors were able to do in practice. Supervisors themselves pointed to longstanding financial pressure, with one noting that “our salaries are very low—it has been the same for the last 15 years” (S2). Supervisors also emphasised the difficulty of sustaining visits and follow-up when transport costs had to be covered personally. As one supervisor who also oversees other supervisors noted, “it’s not reasonable for me to tell a supervisor to go to a school that is 100 km away, or even 70 km away. He needs transportation and travel expenses” (S3).

More broadly, participants also linked low salaries to teacher motivation and engagement, with one noting that “the salary issue made them not want to interact or to prepare for their lessons because they are thinking about how to feed their children” (S1). These accounts suggest that digital supervision was being implemented within material conditions that placed pressure on both delivery and participation, limiting the feasibility of visits, follow-up, and the wider conditions for professional engagement.

3.6.2. Connectivity and infrastructure limitations significantly impacted digital supervision activities

Connectivity and infrastructure limitations emerged as one of the most significant constraints on the implementation of digital supervision. Across interviews, several participants described weak or inconsistent internet access as a persistent barrier, particularly in rural areas where supervision visits were often taking place. These conditions affected whether digital tools could be used as intended during school visits, especially when the

system depended on a live connection for functions such as location verification or report submission. One supervisor explained that “the network there is either weak or non-existent,” which meant that while they could reach the school, they were sometimes unable to complete and submit the required supervision forms on site (S2). Others similarly noted that reports could be delayed because of weak network coverage, with one participant explaining that the report might only be delivered in the evening even if the visit had taken place in the morning.

Interestingly, connectivity issues had a reported knock-on effect on the impact of supervision documentation. One supervisor recounted an example of a successful digital supervision scenario in which supervision reporting is instant, while also hinting that delays could result in superiors viewing reports as less useful or even cause them to doubt the supervisor’s reliability: “when the report arrives after two or three days, it has a different flavour” (S2).

These findings indicate that while digital supervision has the potential to streamline reporting and reduce administrative lag, its effectiveness depends on reliable infrastructure, rendering connectivity issues not merely a minor inconvenience but a significant implementation constraint that shapes whether digital supervision can function reliably in real time. In settings where internet access was weak, interrupted, or absent, the intended advantages of immediacy and streamlined reporting were much harder to realise.

3.6.3. Gender and cultural sensitivity regarding photography and recording affect acceptance of digital supervision

Interview discussions indicated that perceptions regarding the use of photographs and recordings during supervision varied across participants and contexts, and were influenced by gender and cultural norms. Some supervisors reported that documenting classroom activities through photographs was generally accepted as part of programme implementation, including in settings where female teachers were veiled. As one supervisor explained, “We visited female teachers, and most of them were veiled. They don’t mind us taking pictures [...] This is a work programme, and they welcome the idea” (S2).

However, in other cases, female teachers and students were described as reluctant to be photographed for religious or cultural reasons (S1, S3). Teachers similarly highlighted that female colleagues, in particular, might express reservations about photographs or the use of digital devices

during supervision (T1). Supervisors described adapting their practices in response to these sensitivities by ensuring that they seek consent before taking photographs (S3) or take photos “from behind so faces don’t appear” (S3). These perspectives indicate that, while photographic and video documentation formed part of supervision processes, their use was shaped by cultural sensitivities, consent practices, and broader efforts to foster trust within school communities.

3.7. How do participants understand and experience digital security and safeguarding, and how can digital supervision be conducted so as not to compromise participants’ safety, dignity or integrity?

The issues discussed in this section draw on both interview data from participants and written insights from experts (referred to as Expert 1 and Expert 2 as coded in the methodology), and should be interpreted in light of the broader implementation context. In an emergency setting characterised by constrained infrastructure, uneven digital familiarity, and wider cultural norms around authority and acceptable practice, privacy, security, and safeguarding risks may not always be readily recognised or explicitly raised by participants themselves. Highlighting these concerns is therefore not intended to individualise responsibility, but to identify areas where future implementation and scale-up will require stronger support, clearer guidance, and contextually appropriate safeguards.

3.7.1. Teachers have limited awareness of digital privacy and data-protection risks

A recurring finding across the interviews was that teachers had limited awareness of digital privacy and data-protection risks. As noted in [Section 3.4](#), the pilot was conducted in a context of limited digital awareness in general. When asked directly about digital privacy, several teachers expressed little concern, even when prompted to consider possible data misuse: “I don’t mind anything” (T1); “no problem at all” (T2). A supervisor similarly observed that they “work with a digital system, and the teacher has no idea and doesn’t know what that means” (S3). These accounts suggest that limited awareness was not simply a matter of unfamiliarity with digital tools, but a wider gap in understanding around how personal data may be collected, stored, shared, or reused. This is significant because when teachers are not fully aware of how their data is handled, they are less able to recognise weak safeguards, question inappropriate practices, or identify when information may be used beyond its original purpose.

This has important implications for implementation. The digital supervision process may involve collecting observation notes, photographs, and videos, all of which can contain sensitive information about teachers and learners. In principle, such data may be collected to support coaching, documentation, or follow-up. Discussions with the World Bank team suggested that the pilot training did not include content relating to data privacy or was not designed to build teachers' or supervisors' awareness of digital risks.

This has important implications for implementation. If clear boundaries are not established, the same information could be used in a way that is harmful to teachers and learners. This concern was also reflected in input from Expert 1, which highlighted that if personal data is leaked, misused, or interpreted outside its original purpose, teachers could face reputational harm, harassment, or professional consequences. The issue, therefore, is not only whether participants express concern about privacy, but whether they are sufficiently informed and supported to understand the possible risks and downstream uses of their data in practice.

3.7.2. The collection and sharing of visual supervision data are currently guided by individual discretion rather than established protocol, leading to safeguarding risks

The supervision process involved the collection of visual and biometric data of both teachers and learners, which has the potential to induce safeguarding risks. As noted in [Sections 3.1](#) and [3.6](#), collecting visual data was commonplace during the digital supervision pilot. There were occasional references to avoiding photographing the faces of female teachers and female students, but these measures appear to have been down to individual judgements rather than examples of following formal guidance. The data also indicates that others (e.g., male students) may have their pictures taken without consent, constituting a significant safeguarding concern. The fact that no participants referred to guidance documents of this nature suggests that there is limited formal or program-wide guidance available detailing when photographs are appropriate, how they should be taken, and how they should be stored or shared. Interview data suggests that such guidance would be welcomed by teachers and supervisors alike: one supervisor suggested that the programme “should include rules that define the work” (S3), while a teacher similarly stated that any programme “must have clear rules and regulations” (T1).

Reflecting on projects of this nature, Expert 1 described the “improper use of photos and recordings” as the “most concerning risk”, underscoring the

particular sensitivity of visual data in education settings. These concerns and their associated standards are well explained in the available child safeguarding literature. Photographs and videos can reveal a learner or teacher's identity, location, and wider personal context simultaneously, which may increase the potential for harm if such material is leaked or accessed by unauthorised parties. This risk is particularly acute for children, as it could lead to unwanted attention or contact from strangers. If children's data is seen by or shared with malicious actors, then it increases the risk of abuse, harassment, grooming, or even radicalisation ([↑ICO, 2025a](#)).

Given this set of risks, Expert 2 stated that “protecting children's identities should be a priority” and advised that tools of this nature should avoid collecting photos or videos that clearly identify students. This is echoed by formal data standards such as those published by the United Kingdom's Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). The ICO's Children's Code explicitly requires those collecting data to afford children the highest level of privacy by default ([↑ICO, 2024](#)). In parallel, the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) states that the collection and processing of photos or videos that include biometric data requires explicit consent or a strong legal basis ([↑European Union, 2016](#)). More generally, the UNICEF Guidance on AI for Children advises minimal data collection from children and that biometric data should be handled with the highest level of protection ([↑UNICEF Innocenti, 2025](#)).

There are also gender-specific risks that female students or teachers could face that involve “using women's photos, sharing them, and threatening them with exposure”. Social stigma can lead girls or women to feel silenced in such situations, preventing them from seeking help publicly and therefore often leading them to comply with the demands of perpetrators. In one Yemen-based case study within a UN Women report, a technician who was repairing a woman's phone downloaded photos from the device, including pictures of her without her veil. He later uploaded these images online, and when the woman's husband found out, he killed his wife ([↑UN Women, 2022](#)). A highly concerning detail of the case was that the technician was not charged with a crime, as there was no national law with which to prosecute him. The combination of social stigma, lack of consequences for perpetrators, and capabilities of modern technology means that girls and women face particularly acute risks when it comes to the leaking of their images or recordings, indicating that strict guidelines around visual data are crucial in school contexts.

Relatedly, the interview data suggests that safeguarding risks may be heightened where visual material is collected and shared through informal

channels. As noted in [Section 3.1](#), one supervisor referred to sharing photos and videos with teachers via WhatsApp for training purposes. While these practices appear to be understood by staff as practical or beneficial, expert input suggests that informal sharing of this kind can create safeguarding concerns. Expert 2 noted that in similar projects, messaging platforms such as WhatsApp may be used for convenience, increasing the likelihood that photos of classrooms, lessons, or students are shared informally and spread beyond the intended group. Expert 1 added that leakage of such data could, in reality, create a “breach of trust and confidentiality”. The safeguarding concern, therefore, is not only that images are collected, but that identifiable visual material may be reused, forwarded, or viewed by others in ways that are difficult to anticipate or control.

3.7.3 Basic device security measures were in place, but these may not be sufficient, particularly where personal devices were used to record data

Interview data suggests that some basic device security measures were in place, but important uncertainties remained around how sensitive data was stored, shared, and accessed in practice. This is compounded by the lack of official tablets for supervisors, leading to the use of potentially insecure personal devices, such as their own phones.

Expert 1 recommended that “all tablets should be password protected to minimise the risk of data leaking”, while Expert 2 highlighted risks associated with “weak account or device security,” including leaving devices unlocked or sharing passwords. Formal standards often specify a number of additional measures, such as institutional control, that allow a central organisation to control user accounts and access privileges remotely ([↑National Cyber Security Centre, 2026](#); [↑UK Department for Education, 2026](#)). Example use cases include remotely wiping or disabling a stolen or lost device, or the controlling organisation revoking access to a supervisor’s device or stored data if they leave the programme. Other key measures include anti-malware software, firewalls, and ensuring installed software is kept up to date.

In practice, supervisors involved in the pilot described the use of passwords or access codes, with one noting that “definitely there will be a password to open it” (S1) and another referring to “a secret code” (S3), indicating at least partial alignment with the security standards cited above. However, the responses indicated that some supervisors were using personal devices, such as “the phone to photograph certain situations” (S1), and that there is no guarantee of the security of personal devices, nor any way to implement institutional controls or additional security measures set out by key security

standards. The use of personal devices during the pilot, therefore, constitutes a potential data protection risk.

3.7.4. Strong guidance and training on data access, ownership, and management are essential to ensuring effective data protection

While not explicitly mentioned by interviewees, both experts raised the lack of data governance mechanisms as a potential risk in programmes involving multiple stakeholders, such as ministries, non-governmental organisations, and vendors. Expert 2 noted that unclear rules around data ownership and access can result in “sensitive information [...] being accessed by unintended parties,” while Expert 1 emphasised the need for “a clear policy on who has the right to access data and how the data will be stored and for how long the data will be stored.” The data suggests that, in practice, data handling may already extend across multiple devices and channels. As the programme scales, managing who can access data, through which systems, and for what purpose is likely to become increasingly important. In this context, clear access control policies, combined with technical enforcement mechanisms, are important for protecting sensitive data in practice ([↑Microsoft, no date](#)). Without such clarity and enforcement, the risk of unintended disclosure, inconsistent handling, or use beyond the original purpose may increase.

Even where robust data security protocols are in place, supervisors and teachers also need to understand what those protocols require and how to implement them. Supervisors and experts highlighted the importance of training and safer data-handling practices. One supervisor emphasised the need for “comprehensive training” (S1), while Expert 1 noted that data collectors need to “clearly understand the protocol”, and Expert 2 highlighted the importance of training on “responsible data handling and safeguarding”. Building on this, experts also emphasised the need to train supervisors in specific practices, such as replacing names with codes (pseudonymisation) and collecting and storing only data that is strictly necessary (data minimisation); both practices are echoed in the ICO’s Children’s Code ([↑ICO, 2024](#)). These reflections suggest that data protection in this context depends not only on technical safeguards, but also on whether those implementing the tool have a clear and shared understanding of appropriate practice ([↑ICO, 2025b](#)).

4. Conclusion

This report examines how digital classroom supervision was experienced during the pilot study in Yemen, what conditions appeared to support or constrain its implementation, and what would be needed to strengthen its future use. Overall, the findings suggest that digital supervision was viewed positively by the majority of participants and was associated with clear practical benefits, particularly faster reporting, more complete documentation, and easier handling of supervision records. Even among participants without direct experience of the pilot, digital supervision was often seen as a desirable step towards a more modern, continuous, and better-organised supervision practice.

At the same time, the study also shows that these potential benefits were only partially realised during the pilot period. In practice, digital supervision was introduced unevenly and often operated alongside paper-based processes rather than replacing them. The practical uptake of digital supervision depended on whether the wider conditions for implementation were in place, including reliable infrastructure, timely device provision, and alignment between digital tools and existing administrative and reporting processes. Its use was further shaped by weak connectivity, tool design problems, limited local technical support, high supervisor caseloads, transport and financial constraints, and uneven institutional support across locations. These findings suggest that the main challenge is not whether digital supervision is acceptable in principle, but whether the wider operational and institutional conditions are in place for it to function consistently and sustainably in practice.

The findings also highlight that supervision is not experienced only as a technical or administrative process. Across the interviews, participants repeatedly linked successful supervision to trust, transparency, communication, and a supportive professional relationship between supervisors and teachers. While supervisors often described digital supervision as intended for development and improvement rather than punishment, teachers' accounts suggested that observation could still generate anxiety, shape classroom performance, and in some cases be interpreted in more evaluative ways.

Data protection, privacy, security, and safeguarding cannot be treated as secondary concerns. In this context, limited digital awareness among some participants, informal sharing of photographs and recordings, cultural and gender sensitivities around visual data, use of personal devices, and unclear rules regarding access and storage all point to significant risks. The

study therefore suggests that future digital supervision in Yemen will need stronger guidance, training, and accountability, not only to support implementation, but also to ensure that data is handled in ways that protect the safety, dignity, and trust of teachers and learners.

Overall, the findings suggest that digital supervision in Yemen should not be approached simply as a shift from paper- to tablet-based reporting. Rather, it should be understood as a broader implementation and governance challenge. If it is to be strengthened and used responsibly in future, attention will need to be given to the practical foundations for scale-up, including standardisation, training, support, workload, connectivity, and transport, alongside clearer safeguards for data handling, visual documentation, and access control. Under those conditions, digital tools may offer a useful way of improving the timeliness, consistency, continuity, and quality of supervision. Without these conditions, however, the potential benefits of digital supervision are likely to remain partial. Without appropriate safeguards, digital supervision could prove detrimental to the safety and well-being of teachers and learners.

5. Recommendations

The findings document a wide range of challenges affecting the implementation of digital supervision in Yemen, spanning participant readiness, tool design, training, infrastructure, data governance, and broader contextual pressures. From this broader landscape, three conditions stand out as binding constraints that, if left unaddressed, are likely to undermine the effectiveness of all other implementation efforts, regardless of how well they are designed. These were prioritised based on the extent to which they act as preconditions for the system to function, their impact on effectiveness, and the risks they pose to safe implementation. Unlike the wider set of challenges, these are not simply areas for improvement; they are prerequisites for digital supervision to function reliably and responsibly at scale.

- **Weak connectivity and infrastructure** represent the most fundamental bottleneck. Without the ability to complete, store, and synchronise supervision data reliably, and without consistent access to the devices required to do so, the core value proposition of digital supervision cannot be realised. In contexts where connectivity is inconsistent or absent, or where tablet distribution is delayed or incomplete, the system cannot function as intended, regardless of improvements in other areas.
- **Insufficient training and limited local technical support** significantly constrain effective implementation. Supervisors are often required to navigate technical issues, use digital tools, and adapt to new processes without adequate preparation or ongoing support. This reduces consistency in tool use, limits confidence in the system, and increases reliance on informal workarounds that may undermine efficiency, data quality, and data protection.
- **Unclear data governance and safeguarding protocols** introduce risks that cut across all aspects of implementation. In the absence of clear guidance on how data is collected, stored, shared, and protected, digital supervision may expose teachers and learners to privacy and safeguarding risks, particularly where visual data is involved or where personal devices and informal communication channels are used. These risks are especially significant in fragile contexts and may undermine trust, participation, and the ability to scale responsibly.

While other challenges, including workload pressures, financial constraints, tool design limitations, and the continued reliance on paper-based

administrative processes, remain important, their resolution is unlikely to yield sustained improvements unless these core conditions are first in place.

The recommendations below therefore address both implementation and scale-up considerations (see [Section 5.1](#)), as well as data protection and safeguarding issues (see [Section 5.2](#)). Taken together, they reflect the practical, organisational, and governance-related actions needed to make digital supervision more feasible, consistent, and effective, while also helping ensure it is carried out in ways that do not compromise the safety, dignity, or privacy of those involved. Where appropriate, the research team has indicated which actors may be best placed to take forward the proposed actions, while recognising that final decisions will need to be made by the World Bank, Save the Children, and the Ministry of Education.

To support clearer decision-making and implementation planning, the recommendations are prioritised using a simple, colour-coded classification system and accompanied by a high-level overview of the resource implications. Together, these reflect the binding constraints identified above and the practical sequencing required in a resource-constrained and fragile context.

- ● **Red — Immediate priority (0–6 months):** Actions required to enable system functionality and address safeguarding risks.
- ● **Amber — Medium-term priority (6–18 months):** Actions that strengthen implementation quality, consistency, and effectiveness.
- ● **Green — Longer-term priority (18+ months):** Actions supporting system strengthening and sustainability.

Each recommendation is also assigned an indicative cost level¹:

- **Low:** Primarily requiring time, coordination, or policy decisions with minimal additional budget.
- **Moderate:** Requiring some dedicated resource allocation, such as training facilitation, tool development, or local focal point designation.
- **High:** Requiring significant investment in procurement, staffing, or sustained programme resourcing.

¹ These are indicative estimates intended to support prioritisation, not precise cost projections.

It is important to note that cost level and urgency do not always align in predictable ways. Several of the most immediate priorities are low cost, precisely because they address binding constraints through policy decisions and guidance rather than financial investment. Conversely, some higher-cost actions are longer term in nature because they require structural or financing arrangements that cannot be put in place quickly.

5.1 Recommendations for digital supervision implementation

● 1. Strengthen infrastructure to ensure digital supervision readiness.

Responsible actors: Ministry of Education; implementing partners.

Priority classification: Red — Immediate priority (0–6 months)

Indicative cost level: High

Reliable infrastructure should be treated as a precondition for digital supervision, not an assumption. In contexts where connectivity is inconsistent and access to functioning devices is uneven, implementation depends not only on improving software functionality but on ensuring the minimum infrastructure required for supervisors to use the system reliably in practice.

This should begin with an access and infrastructure readiness mapping exercise, if not already completed, to assess current conditions across implementation areas, including supervisor access to tablets, connectivity coverage, charging arrangements, and device functionality.

Priority actions could include:

- **Ensuring timely and equitable access to tablets for all supervisors**, including resolving delays in tablet distribution and addressing gaps in availability across locations.
- **Strengthening connectivity and power support arrangements**, including provision or maintenance of SIM cards in tablets, use of mobile data synchronisation where real-time connectivity is unreliable, and ensuring access to functioning docking stations/portable Wi-Fi devices (mobile Wi-Fi/MiFi) and charging arrangements to support device readiness.

- **Adopting an offline-first and delayed synchronisation approach** in low-connectivity settings, allowing supervision data to be captured during visits and uploaded once connectivity becomes available.
- **Introducing minimum infrastructure readiness criteria for scale-up**, so deployment is sequenced in ways that reflect connectivity realities rather than assuming uniform conditions².

Strengthening these foundational conditions would help address one of the core binding constraints identified in the analysis and improve the feasibility, reliability, and fidelity of digital supervision implementation.

● **2. Establish formal guidelines and protocols for digital supervision practices and data governance.**

Responsible actors: Ministry of Education; World Bank; implementing partners; Save the Children; third-party technology providers

Priority classification: Red – Immediate priority (0–6 months)

Indicative cost level: Moderate

If digital supervision is to scale, clearer and more consistent procedures will be needed for both how supervision is conducted in practice and how related data is handled over time. Current findings suggest that uneven implementation, hybrid documentation practices, and limited clarity around data ownership, access, storage, and sharing have contributed to fragmentation and uncertainty. These risks may become more significant as implementation expands and more actors become involved.

Formal guidelines and protocols should therefore establish the minimum procedures and responsibilities required for safe and consistent supervision. Initial versions should be developed and introduced during the early phase of implementation, with further refinement as supervision practices stabilise.

Essential procedures to establish first (to enable safe and consistent implementation):

- How the tool is introduced to supervisors, teachers, and schools
- What supervisors are expected to do during and after a visit
- How observations are documented

² This recommendation is also consistent with design principles reflected in the proposed *Sustaining Education and Learning (SEAL) Project Appraisal Document*, particularly its emphasis on adaptive implementation, access criteria, and strengthened data systems.

- What forms of evidence are acceptable
- How teachers are informed about the process and its purpose
- What data are collected and for what purpose
- Who can access different forms of data, including raw and summary data
- What procedures should be followed in the event of misuse, breach, or unauthorised access

Additional procedures to strengthen implementation over time:

- How photographs or recordings should be handled
- Where data is stored and for how long
- Whether data can be downloaded, transferred, or shared beyond the immediate programme team
- What access control measures and permissions apply across partner organisations
- What contact points or complaint routes are available if concerns arise

These steps would reduce fragmentation across governorates and directorates, support more consistent supervision practices, strengthen data governance across partner organisations, and help maintain trust in how supervision processes and related data are managed over time.

● **3. Simplify tool design and improve usability.**

Responsible actors: Implementing partners, tool developers, and the Ministry of Education.

Priority classification: Red—Immediate priority (0–6 months)

Indicative cost level: Moderate

The tool should be designed for practical use during school visits, with greater attention to usability, flexibility, and the realities of field implementation. This could include:

- Removing or relaxing mandatory features that are difficult to complete in the field, such as sharing live locations
- Allowing entries to be edited when mistakes are made
- Ensuring school codes are accurately reflected in the digital system
- Shortening long tools so they can be completed more efficiently during visits

These changes would improve the usability and functionality of the tool during supervision visits. They would also reduce delays, improve data quality, and strengthen the reliability and completeness of submitted data.

● **4. Establish clear local technical support and escalation routes.**

Responsible actors: Implementing partners, Ministry of Education

Priority classification: Red—Immediate priority (0–6 months)

Indicative cost level: Low

Supervisors should have access to timely technical support at the governorate or directorate level, rather than relying primarily on informal peer assistance. This could include:

- Assigning named focal points for technical issues at the local level (these could be supervisors with particular experience or interest in digital approaches)
- Setting out clear escalation routes when problems cannot be resolved locally
- Providing rapid support for issues such as syncing failures, login problems, or malfunctioning devices
- Ensuring support is available during active implementation periods, not only at the start of the programme

These measures would reduce delays and improve confidence in the system's responsiveness.

● **5. Allocate budget explicitly for transport and fieldwork costs.**

Responsible actors: World Bank, implementing partners, Ministry of Education

Priority classification: Green—Longer-term priority (18+ months)

Indicative cost level: High

Long distances and out-of-pocket costs reduce supervisors' ability to conduct visits and follow up. Including realistic transport costs in programme design would improve implementation feasibility and support more consistent supervision. This could include:

- Allocating funds for travel to remote schools
- Covering repeat visits where follow-up is expected

- Budgeting for fuel or local transport reimbursement
- Distinguishing between routine visits and higher-cost visits to harder-to-reach locations

These measures would improve the feasibility of supervision activities and support more reliable implementation across locations.

● 6. Strengthen training and ongoing support for digital supervision.

Responsible actors: Ministry of Education; implementing partners; supervisors.

Priority classification: Red—Immediate priority (0–6 months)

Indicative cost level: Moderate

Study findings suggest that supervisors require stronger and more sustained support to participate effectively in digital supervision. Limited digital literacy and limited criticality of digital processes may affect their ability to participate in an informed way and to recognise weak safeguards or inappropriate practices. Supervisors need more than one-off orientation to use devices, complete observation forms, submit data, review records, and resolve common errors in practice.

Training should therefore go beyond basic introduction and include practical, repeated, and role-appropriate support over time.

Immediate priorities for safe and effective implementation

- Initial training for supervisors on how to use the device, complete observation forms, and submit data
- Refresher sessions after early implementation experience
- Training on how to review records and resolve common errors

Ongoing actions to strengthen practice and sustainability

- A cascading model in which trained supervisors support teachers to better understand the process and its implications
- Broader digital skills training beyond basic tool navigation
- Training that strengthens digital and critical digital literacy, including understanding privacy, data protection, and responsible data handling

This would help address uneven digital familiarity, strengthen informed participation, and support more consistent and responsible

implementation. It would also help reduce operational errors, improve data quality, and, over time, strengthen confidence in the supervision process.

● **7. Reinforce teacher awareness of digital supervision objectives and processes.**

Responsible actors: Ministry of Education, implementing partners, supervisors

Priority classification: Red—Immediate priority (0–6 months)

Indicative cost level: Low

Teachers currently appear to have limited awareness of how digital supervision works, what data may be collected, and what privacy or data protection risks may arise. They also appear to be unclear about why digital supervision is conducted. Clear and consistent communication about the purpose of supervision and how it works in practice is essential to ensure that teachers understand what to expect and how they can benefit in terms of professional development.

This could include:

- Orientation for teachers on how digital supervision works, what data is collected, and what safeguards should be in place
- Explaining to teachers what the tool is for and how the information collected during visits will be used
- Making observation criteria more visible and understandable to teachers before and during supervision visits
- Ensuring supervisors provide feedback during or after visits, rather than only recording information silently
- Communicating clearly that the purpose of visits is improvement and professional support, not surveillance or sanction
- Reinforcing this message consistently in training materials, supervision guidance, and routine communication with schools

Where feasible, this messaging should be integrated into routine supervision practice, rather than delivered as a one-time explanation at the start of implementation.

Greater transparency around purpose and process may help strengthen trust, improve teacher engagement during visits, and support more open and constructive supervision interactions over time.

● **8. Design digital supervision to support repeated visits, feedback, and follow-up over time, not only one-off reporting.**

Responsible actors: World Bank, Ministry of Education, implementing partners

Priority classification: Amber—Medium-term priority (6–18 months)

Indicative cost level: Moderate

Digital supervision should support continuity in supervisory practice rather than functioning only as a reporting tool. This could include:

- Enabling supervisors to access and review previous visit records during school visits
- Allowing supervisors to track whether earlier feedback has been acted upon
- Including fields to record follow-up actions and next steps
- Enabling supervisors to flag teachers or schools for repeat visits or additional support
- Ensuring programme design allows for multiple visits per teacher per year, rather than one-off observations

These features are important because participants linked effective supervision to the ability to revisit teachers, monitor progress, and provide follow-up support. Without this, digital tools may improve reporting speed without strengthening the developmental value of supervision.

● **9. Optimise supervisor workload within existing resources.**

Responsible actors: Ministry of Education, implementing partners

Priority classification: Amber—Medium-term priority (6–18 months)

Indicative cost level: Low

Heavy caseloads limit the depth of classroom engagement and reduce the likelihood of meaningful follow-up. While broader structural reforms may take longer, some improvements can be made within existing resources by adjusting expectations and planning arrangements. This could include:

- Prioritising follow-up for teachers needing additional support
- Setting more realistic expectations for the number of visits possible within a term
- Aligning digital reporting requirements with the time available for observation and feedback

These adjustments could help improve the quality and manageability of supervision without requiring major additional investment.

● **10. Strengthen supervisor workforce capacity over time.**

Responsible actors: Ministry of Education, implementing partners

Priority classification: Green — Longer-term priority (18+ months)

Indicative cost level: High

Some workload pressures are unlikely to be resolved through planning adjustments alone and may require longer-term structural investment. Strengthening supervisor capacity over time would help ensure that supervision remains manageable, effective, and sustainable as digital supervision systems expand. This could include:

- Reducing the number of teachers assigned to each supervisor, where possible
- Increasing staffing levels where feasible
- Ensuring sustainable financing for supervision roles

These changes may require adjustments to staffing models, financing arrangements, and supervision planning processes, and are therefore likely to take time to implement.

The recommendations relating to digital supervision implementation, including their assigned priority rating, indicative cost level, and explanatory notes, are summarised in [Table 2](#) below.

Table 2. *Recommendations for digital supervision implementation*

Rec #	Recommendation	Priority area	Indicative cost level	Notes
1	Strengthen infrastructure to ensure digital supervision readiness.	Red (0–6 months)	High	Requires upfront investment in connectivity support, device readiness, and infrastructure mapping across implementation areas.
2	Establish formal guidelines and protocols for digital supervision practices and data governance.	Red (0–6 months)	Moderate	Infrastructure cost of supplying all supervisors with tablets and ensuring they use them rather than personal devices
3	Simplify tool design and improve usability	Red (0–6 months)	Moderate	One-off technical investment to improve tool usability and functionality, including simplification of forms and adjustments to key features.
4	Establish clear local technical support and escalation routes	Red (0–6 months)	Low	Focal point designation within existing staff; assuming no new hiring is required in most cases, as additional recruitment could affect the indicative cost level.
5	Allocate budget explicitly for transport and fieldwork costs	Green (18+ months)	High	Recurring operational cost; requires an explicit budget line in programme design and donor planning.

Rec #	Recommendation	Priority area	Indicative cost level	Notes
6	Strengthen training and ongoing support for digital supervision.	Red (0–6 months)	Moderate	Recurring cost per training cycle; depends on geographic coverage and number of supervisors reached
7	Reinforce teacher awareness of digital supervision objectives and processes.	Red (0–6 months)	Low	Communication and training integration; requires sustained messaging over time rather than one-off action
8	Design digital supervision to support repeated visits, feedback, and follow-up over time, not only one-off reporting	Amber (6–18 months)	Moderate	Requires iterative tool redesign and programme planning adjustments across partner organisations
9	Optimise supervisor workload within existing resources	Amber (6–18 months)	Low	Primarily involves management and planning adjustments within existing resources, with minimal additional financial investment.
10	Strengthen supervisor workforce capacity over time	Green (18+ months)	High	Structural investment in staffing and supervisor-to-teacher ratios; requires sustained financing arrangements

5.2 Recommendations for data privacy and safeguarding

This section presents specific recommendations on data protection and safeguarding. These recommendations are high priority but relatively low cost. Most involve policy clarification, procedural guidance, and strengthened practice rather than major financial investment. All of the issues outlined below should be addressed before wide-scale implementation. Without appropriate safeguards, there is a risk of harm to learners and teachers and a risk to programme effectiveness and public trust.

These recommendations are presented separately from the operational recommendations because they address foundational risk management requirements. Many implementation improvements can be introduced over time as systems develop. In contrast, safeguarding and data protection measures must be established early in the implementation process; weak safeguards can create immediate risk even when other programme components are functioning as intended.

- **1. Standardise digital supervision data practices through a unified data platform.**

Responsible actors: Ministry of Education, World Bank, implementing partners, Save the Children, third-party technology providers.

Priority level: Red (0–6 months)

Indicative cost level: Moderate

If digital supervision is to scale, clearer, more consistent and enforceable data handling procedures will be needed. Current findings suggest that uneven implementation, hybrid documentation practices, and limited clarity around data ownership, access, storage, and sharing have contributed to fragmentation, uncertainty, and increased risk of data leaks. These risks may become more significant as implementation expands and more actors become involved.

To mitigate these risks, data protection protocols can be operationalised using platforms that provide technical access control mechanisms and enforce data governance rules. Platforms such as Google Workspace or Microsoft 365 are mature products that offer these capabilities and centralise organisational data control in one place. This creates control over who has access to data, for how long, and whether data can be shared, and enables implementation leaders to revoke access with ease. Additionally,

these platforms are built for scale, minimising risk as implementation scales up and new actors get involved. However, this also requires that supervisors use only the chosen platform for uploading and sharing recorded data, and thus needs to be embedded into their training and guidelines.

Formal guidelines and protocols should therefore define:

- How the tool is introduced to supervisors, teachers, and schools
- What supervisors are expected to do during and after a visit
- How observations are documented
- What forms of evidence are acceptable
- How photographs or recordings should be handled
- How teachers are informed about the process and its purpose
- What data is collected and for what purpose
- Who can access different forms of data, including raw data, summary data, and dashboards
- Where data is stored and for how long
- Whether data can be downloaded, transferred, or shared beyond the immediate programme team
- What access control measures and permissions apply across partner organisations
- What procedures should be followed in the event of misuse, breach, or unauthorised access
- What contact points or complaint routes are available if concerns arise

Immediate priorities for safe and effective implementation should include:

- Writing and publishing formal privacy policies that answer the questions above.
- Operationalising these policies using a platform that provides technical access control mechanisms and enforces data governance rules. For example, Google Workspace allows an organisation to control who has access to data, how long data gets stored, etc.
- Training supervisors to only use the chosen platform

These steps would reduce fragmentation across governorates and directorates, support more consistent implementation, strengthen data governance across partner organisations, and help maintain trust in how supervision processes and related data are managed over time.

● **2. Minimise the use and sharing of identifiable photos and recordings.**

Responsible actors: Ministry of Education, implementing partners, supervisors, teachers

Priority level: Red (0–6 months)

Indicative cost level: Low

Photographs and recordings should be used only where necessary, with clear guidance on consent, anonymity, and culturally sensitive practice. This is particularly important given that the improper use of visual data was identified as a significant safeguarding risk within the study findings, and leaked or inappropriately shared images could expose learners and teachers to harm, harassment, or reputational risk. In the case of female students and teachers, identifiable images may carry heightened risk in contexts where photography is culturally sensitive.

Good practice in this respect could include:

- Avoiding identifiable images of learners wherever possible
- Avoiding pictures or videos of children unless there is a clear and justified need
- Limiting photographs of female teachers or students, where this may be culturally sensitive
- Using non-identifiable alternatives, such as photos from behind or without faces, only where justified
- Prohibiting the routine informal sharing of classroom images through channels such as WhatsApp
- Providing explicit guidance on when visual documentation is and is not appropriate

Immediate priorities for safe and effective implementation include:

- Devoting a section of the initial training for supervisors to discuss the risks around taking and sharing identifiable pictures or videos
- Re-clarifying which communication channels are not permitted, such as WhatsApp

Ongoing actions to strengthen practice and sustainability include:

- A cascading model in which trained supervisors explain these data privacy considerations to teachers so that they can better understand and point out when best practices are not being followed.

These measures would help reduce safeguarding and privacy risks and better protect the safety, dignity, and identities of learners and teachers.

● **3. Use pseudonymisation to reduce data risks.**

Responsible actors: Implementing partners, technology providers, Ministry of Education, research partners

Priority level: Red (0–6 months)

Indicative cost level: Low

- Experts recommended implementing immediate pseudonymisation for both teachers and learners. This is a safer data practice that prevents linking observation logs to a real person's identity.
- Mitigates the majority of personal risks if data were to be leaked. This protects professional trust and reduces the risk of teachers facing reputational harm or harassment.

Immediate priorities for safe and effective implementation include:

- Including pseudonymisation as a core tool design requirement to systematically limit the ability of supervisors to link observation logs to a real person's identity in their entries.

Ongoing actions to strengthen practice and sustainability:

- Semi-regular checks or audits by data professionals to verify that specific observation logs cannot be easily linked to actual persons.

● **4. Avoid the use of personal or unmanaged messaging platforms for supervision data.**

Responsible actors: Ministry of Education, implementing partners, supervisors, school and governorate-level managers.

Priority level: Red (0–6 months)

Indicative cost level: Low

Supervision data should not be shared through personal or unmanaged messaging platforms such as WhatsApp, particularly where photographs, videos, or personally identifiable information are involved. Steps to ensure that this does not happen could include:

- Using only organisation-managed platforms with administrative control for communication or file-sharing, for example, approved systems such as Microsoft Teams, Google Workspace tools, or other centrally managed platforms

- Restricting the sharing of supervision data to approved professional channels
- Prohibiting the sharing of identifiable classroom images, recordings, or observation data through personal messaging applications
- Providing clear guidance on which platforms are approved for different types of communication
- Integrating communication and data exchange within the digital supervision system, where feasible

This would strengthen institutional control over sensitive data and reduce the risk of inappropriate access, retention, or onward sharing.

Immediate priorities for safe and effective implementation include:

- Selecting and setting up a managed platform, such as Google Workspace, for communication and file-sharing with proper administrative controls configured.
- During training, clarifying which communication platforms are approved and which are not, and the rationale for these restrictions.
- Placing restrictions on the devices themselves to reduce the risk (e.g. not permitting the installation of apps such as WhatsApp or other informal sharing apps)

Ongoing actions to strengthen practice and sustainability include:

Beyond not personally using unmanaged messaging platforms, training supervisors to be vigilant of others doing so and having an accessible, confidential mechanism that they can use to report malpractice, thereby enforcing the idea that “data protection is the responsibility of all”.

The recommendations relating to data privacy and safeguarding, including their assigned priority rating, indicative cost level, and explanatory notes, are summarised in [Table 3](#) below.

Table 3. *Recommendations for data privacy and safeguarding*

Rec #	Recommendation	Priority rating	Indicative cost level	Notes
1	Standardise digital supervision data practices through a unified platform.	Red (0–6 months)	Moderate	Development of privacy policy and data protection protocols; no procurement required. High importance, as this is a precondition for responsible scale-up. Configuration of an organisation-controlled platform and device controls will require some technical skill, but should require minimal additional operational costs, as this is a one-off technical investment.
2	Minimise the use and sharing of identifiable photos and recordings.	Red (0–6 months)	Low	Guidance and communication only; can be embedded in training delivery
3	Use pseudonymisation to reduce data risks	Red (0–6 months)	Low	Technical design of existing tool; minimal additional cost once protocols are in place
4	Avoid the use of personal or unmanaged messaging platforms for supervision data.	Red (0–6 months)	Low	Requires behaviour change over time; training (on what may/may not be shared) should be issued immediately as a low-cost first step.

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